

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART V. SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS. CINNAMIC ACID

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Cinnamic acid precipitates thorium completely from boiling solutions above the pH 1.9. The precipitate, though flocculent in the beginning, collects on boiling and settles down quickly. Cerite earths in concentrations up to fifty-fold may be separated in a single operation in the pH range 2.0–2.6. Thorium in monazite extract, freed from zirconium and phosphate, has been accurately estimated at pH 2.0 and 2.6.

Kolb and Ahrle (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1905, 18, 92) employed, amongst others, cinnamic acid for the precipitation of thorium, but abandoned the reagent in favour of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid. In this communication are reported the results of an extensive investigation on the use of cinnamic acid as a precipitant for thorium and as a reagent for the separation of rare earths therefrom; the only rare earths tried are the cerite earths occurring in the monazite. At pH 1.9 and above, cinnamic acid gives a white voluminous precipitate with thorium which on boiling for a few minutes assumes a more crystalline form and settles quickly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents Employed.—The preparation of thorium nitrate solution and that of cerite earths is described in an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457). Cinnamic acid, B. D. H. reagent grade, was further purified by crystallisation from boiling water.

Estimation.—Thorium nitrate solution (10 ml.) was diluted to 100 ml. and heated to boiling. Boiling 0.5% cinnamic acid (100 ml.) was gradually added with stirring. The liquid was then boiled for 15 to 20 minutes during which time the flocculent precipitate of thorium cinnamate collected and settled down. It was filtered hot after 20 minutes through a 11 cm. Whatman No. 41 filter, washed with cold water and ignited wet to the oxide. For every 0.1 g. of thorium dioxide present 1 g. of the reagent was sufficient. Thorium dioxide obtained was 0.0624 g. Estimation by the *m*-nitrobenzoic acid method gave 0.0625 g. By this method as little as 0.0006 g. of thorium dioxide can be estimated accurately.

Effect of pH.—Since earlier reports (*loc. cit.*) rejected the reagent as unsatisfactory and the separation from other elements generally rests on a control of pH , the precipitation of thorium by the reagent under varying conditions of pH has been investigated. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

*Effect of pH on the precipitation of thorium*ThO₂ taken = 0.0625 g. Total volume of the solution = 200 ml.

Expt. No.	pH of the final soln.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Diff.	Expt. No.	pH of the final soln.	ThO ₂ obtained.	Diff.
1	4.0	0.0625 g.	0.0 mg.	9	2.2	0.0624 g.	-0.1 mg.
2	3.6	0.0624	-0.1	10	2.0	0.0623	-0.2
3	3.4	0.0625	0.0	11	1.9	0.0624	-0.1
4	3.2	0.0626	+0.1	12	1.8	0.0618	-0.7
5	3.0	0.0624	-0.1	13	1.6	0.0610	-1.5
6	2.8	0.0625	0.0*	14	1.5	0.0594	-3.1
7	2.6	0.0624	-0.1	15	1.4	0.0520	-10.5
8	2.4	0.0623	-0.2	16	1.25	0.0025	-60.0
				17	1.15	0.0000	-62.5

Separation from Cerite Earths.—The precipitation of thorium is not complete below pH 1.9 and the cerite earths are precipitated above 3.2. Even at pH 2.8 slight contamination of the thoria with cerite earths occurs. Preliminary investigations have shown that good results could be obtained in the pH range 2.0 to 2.6. Two series of investigations, one at pH 2.0 and the other at pH 2.6, are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

ThO₂ taken = 0.0625 g.

Expt. No.	R ₂ O ₃ added (cerite earths)	ThO ₂ obtained (pH 2.0).	ThO ₂ obtained (pH 2.6).	Expt. No.	R ₂ O ₃ added (cerite earths).	ThO ₂ obtained (pH 2.0).	ThO ₂ obtained (pH 2.6).
1	0.064 g.	0.0624 g.	0.0625 g.	6	0.640 g.	0.0624 g.	0.0623 g.
2	0.128	0.0626	0.0625	7	1.280	0.0626	0.0623
3	0.256	0.0623	0.0624	8	1.920	0.0625	0.0626
4	0.320	0.0625	0.0624	9	2.560	0.0624	0.0627*
5	0.512	0.0625	0.0625	10	3.200	0.0627*	0.0630*

* ThO₂ is slightly coloured.

Thus, a fifty-fold excess of cerite earths is removed in a single precipitation.

Determination of Thorium in Monazite.—Thorium in monazite extract, freed from zirconium and phosphate⁷ (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*), was estimated with this reagent at pH 2.0 and 2.6. For comparison the results obtained after a double precipitation with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid are included in Table III.

TABLE III

Estimation of monazite.

Expt. No.	Vol. of monazite extract taken.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	ThO ₂ obtained with cinnamic acid at	
			pH 2.0.	pH 2.6.
1	10 g.	0.0650 g.	0.0650 g.	0.0648 g.
2	10	0.0650	0.0649	0.0650
3	20	0.1300	0.1302	0.1301
4	20	0.1300	0.1330	0.1299
5	1*	0.0065†	0.0066	0.0065
6	0.1*	0.00065†	0.0006	0.0007

† Theoretical.

* A micro-pipette was employed.

Composition of the Precipitate.—Thorium cinnamate, precipitated as described above, has a slightly varying composition. Two different samples of the dried precipitate, weighing 0.1435 g. and 0.1272 g., gave on ignition 0.0492 g. and 0.0443 g. of ThO₂ respectively. These values indicate the association of three molecules of cinnamic acid with one thorium ion together with four molecules of water. It is not possible to weigh the precipitate directly, but ignition to the oxide is essential.

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"We gladly accede to the request of Dr. D. Chakravarti, Hon. Secretary of the Indian Chemical Society, to print the following letter addressed to us, and offer our sincere apologies for having misrepresented the practice of Indian chemists in publishing their papers :—

"On behalf of the Indian Chemical Society I beg to invite your kind attention to a statement on page 93, Vol. 74 (1950) of your esteemed Journal: "although the Indian Chemical Society has recently celebrated its Jubilee, most of the leading Indian chemists appear still to prefer the *Journal of the Chemical Society* to the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* as a medium for publication."

As a matter of fact Indian Students working in foreign countries sometimes find it convenient to publish their papers in the Journals of those countries. Authors of papers from India, except only one or two, seldom seek publication in foreign Journals.

I would request you, therefore, to publish this letter in your Journal by way of rectifying the misconception that has arisen out of the statement referred to above."

Ed.